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Student Entrance Knowledge, Expectations, and Motivation within Introductory Programming Courses in Portugal and Serbia

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ABSTRACT

Programming is a skill needed across various disciplines and it is becoming more valuable for many job positions. However, students still appear to struggle in introductory programming courses. Academic achievement in programming may be influenced by numerous factors and may vary across countries, as observed in a previous study focused on Portugal and Serbia. In the present study, factors generally related to achievement and attrition, namely student entrance knowledge, expectations, and motivation, were examined as possible reasons behind achievement issues in introductory programming. An anonymous questionnaire that comprised closed-ended items was given to students enrolled in introductory programming courses at technically oriented higher education institutions in Portugal and Serbia. After data cleansing, response data from 678 students were quantitatively analysed to identify overall characteristics of the investigated groups, as well as differences between the groups from the two countries.

The students generally had numerous expectations and motives regarding introductory programming, but their reported entrance knowledge of programming was generally at low levels. On average, the groups from the two countries were similar. The main differences include higher entrance knowledge for students from Serbia and slightly higher expectations for students from Portugal. These findings form a basis for further inquiry into causes of previously observed student performance variations between Portugal and Serbia. As there are many commonalities between the students from these countries, we may work on novel instruction methods and tools that would be useful for programming teachers and enrolled students in both countries.

1 INTRODUCTION

Computer science skills, including programming, are becoming more important in various industries [1]. As a result, higher education institutions (HEIs) are under great pressure to provide students with a wider and more advanced set of competences. As opposed to the projections that the demand for programming skills will grow [2], there have been indications of university students generally struggling with programming in introductory computing courses [3].

Similar trends have been noticed in practice by teachers in Portugal and Serbia, which eventually led to the start of a bilateral research project between the two

countries in 2018. This project initially focused on analysing teaching and achievement in programming education and it was soon observed that the two countries considerably differed in student pass and assessment rates within introductory programming courses [4]. In some cases, the pass rates were below the global average pass rate for such courses. These findings, together with the general goal of having more competent graduates in both countries, have prompted a new inquiry into student characteristics and attitudes relevant for academic achievement and the study of programming.

The present study investigates student entrance knowledge, expectations, and motivation as factors that could be used both to explain the observed differences and influence adoption of new competences by students. The following research questions are examined:

- What are the overall entrance knowledge, expectations, and motivation of students enrolled in introductory programming courses in Portugal and Serbia?
- How do students enrolled in introductory programming courses differ between Portugal and Serbia in terms of their entrance knowledge, expectations, and motivation?

These questions were answered by conducting a survey at HEIs in Portugal and Serbia, including HEIs that participated in the previous study [4], and analysing collected data using multiple data analysis methods.

2 RELATED WORK

Student entrance knowledge, expectations and motivation were the three main factors explored in the present study as there is considerable research about their relations with academic achievement and attrition.

In engineering education, students who persisted in engineering had greater personal, academic, or experiential exposure to engineering as opposed to students who switched to other fields [5]. Learning programming before university could be associated with higher initial academic achievement in ICT-related studies [6]. There is additional evidence of a weak positive relationship between programming performance at the university level and previous computer experience, albeit without statistical significance [7].

Unfulfilled student expectations may lead to various disappointments and even withdrawal from higher education [8]. Students may have expectations towards course content, in particular its academic rigour and alignment with industry perspectives [9]. Furthermore, expectations may vary with gender, as demonstrated in a survey of student perceptions of a computing-related programme [10].

A varied set of reasons may be behind enrolment in higher education and selection of a particular degree. In a study concerning motivation of students in computing-related studies, the compulsoriness of a programming module was the main reason

for taking the module, much stronger than learning or actual module content [11]. However, the need to motivate students in programming has already been recognized [12]. Moreover, a positive relationship between intrinsic motivation and programming performance was discovered for a group of students in an introductory programming module [13].

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Overview

A quantitative research design was used in the present study. A survey was developed to investigate student entrance knowledge, expectations and motivation in introductory programming courses at four technically oriented HEIs: three from Portugal and one from Serbia. Collected quantitative data were first processed and then analysed using quantitative methods.

3.2 Survey

Students were surveyed by using an anonymous questionnaire in English. The questionnaire consisted of 21 close-ended items, here grouped into four categories:

- CAT0: four introductory items about student background, e.g., current study programme and previous education;
- CAT1: three items about entrance knowledge related to programming, e.g., familiarity with algorithm concepts and knowledge of programming languages;
- CAT2: six items about expectations regarding the introductory programming course, e.g., to learn a programming language and to develop software; and
- CAT3: eight items about motivation regarding programming, e.g., preference for using algorithms to specify reasoning and fulfilment in finding a solution.

For each item, exactly one response was to be selected. A 5-point response scale (1 – Null, 2 – Reduced, 3 – Medium, 4 – High, 5 – Excellent) was used for the CAT1 items, while a 3-point response scale (1 – Disagree, 2 – Neutral, 3 – Agree) was used for the CAT2 and CAT3 items.

The survey was conducted at the participating HEIs in the middle of the winter semester of the academic year 2018/2019. In total, there were 736 respondents (407 in Portugal and 329 in Serbia).

3.3 Data processing

The initial data set was based on 22 variables and contained 736 records, one record for each respondent. One variable denoted the country of the respondent, while the remaining 21 variables denoted responses to the 21 questionnaire items.

All records that contained an invalid response value for some item not related to study programme enrolment were excluded from the data set. A response value was considered invalid if the respondent provided a response value not listed in the questionnaire, provided multiple response values, or did not provide any response value at all. After record exclusion, 678 records remained in the data set: 389

records of respondents from Portugal and 289 records of respondents from Serbia. This somewhat strict exclusion criterion was adopted because it facilitated the subsequent analysis process. The analysis considerably depended on three derived variables, whose derivation required clean records across 17 initial variables. The exclusion criterion was regarded as acceptable also because a high number of the initial records were retained after the exclusion (approximately 92%).

3.4 Data analysis

For the purpose of detecting overall differences in responses between Portugal and Serbia, the data set was extended by adding three new variables: *Mean Entrance Knowledge*, *Mean Expectations*, and *Mean Motivation*, which correspond to averaged responses to the items in the categories CAT1, CAT2, and CAT3, respectively. Overall differences in responses were first examined by comparing means (M), standard deviations (SD), medians (Mdn), and distributions of the variables *Mean Entrance Knowledge*, *Mean Expectations*, and *Mean Motivation*.

Differences in responses between the two countries were evaluated by statistical testing. Independence between the country variable and each item response variable from the item categories CAT1, CAT2, and CAT3 was tested using the two-tailed Fisher's exact test. As the test was applied 17 times, i.e., once for each considered item response variable, the Bonferroni-Holm method for p value adjustment was used to control the error of the first kind in multiple testing [14]. In each testing, the null hypothesis was that the distribution of responses to the analysed item did not differ between Portugal and Serbia. The result of individual testing was considered statistically significant if the adjusted p value was below the 0.05 level. Mosaic plots were used to visualise distributions of responses to the items for which statistically significant results were obtained.

All analyses were conducted using the *R* language and environment for statistical computation², the integrated development environment *RStudio Desktop Open Source Edition*³, and the following additional *R* packages with their dependencies⁴: *tables*, and *RColorBrewer*.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Overall responses to items

As evidenced by descriptive statistics reported in *Table 1*, respondents in Portugal and Serbia possess low entrance knowledge of programming (M = 2.25, Mdn = 2.00, Scale 1–5), but have many expectations (M = 2.71, Mdn = 2.83, Scale 1–3), and motives regarding programming (M = 2.63, Mdn = 2.62, Scale 1–3).

The largest difference between the two countries is in mean entrance knowledge, which is higher in Serbia, followed by the difference in mean expectations, which are

² R: The R project for statistical computing, URL: <https://www.r-project.org>

³ Open source and enterprise-ready professional software for data science - RStudio, URL: <https://www.rstudio.com>

⁴ The comprehensive R archive network, URL: <https://cran.r-project.org>

only slightly higher in Portugal. However, the differences in overall responses between Portugal and Serbia appear to be small. This may also be observed in Fig. 1, which contains notched box plots for the respective variables.

Table 1. Descriptive statistics for Mean Entrance Knowledge, Mean Expectations, and Mean Motivation for Portugal and Serbia

Country	n	Mean Entrance Knowledge (Scale 1–5)			Mean Expectations (Scale 1–3)			Mean Motivation (Scale 1–3)		
		M	SD	Mdn	M	SD	Mdn	M	SD	Mdn
Portugal	389	2.14	0.84	2.00	2.72	0.34	2.83	2.64	0.29	2.62
Serbia	289	2.38	0.94	2.33	2.70	0.26	2.67	2.62	0.24	2.62
all	678	2.25	0.89	2.00	2.71	0.31	2.83	2.63	0.27	2.62

Box plots for Mean Entrance Knowledge, Mean Expectations, and Mean Motivation of respondents from Portugal and Serbia

Fig. 1. Distributions of Mean Entrance Knowledge, Mean Expectations, and Mean Motivation for Portugal and Serbia

4.2 Responses to particular items

Responses significantly differed between Portugal and Serbia only for the following two items from the motivation-related category CAT3: *Do you find challenging to code algorithms and run programs?* (adjusted p value = 0.002) and *Do you like the 'trial & error' method to develop solutions?* (adjusted p value = 0.049). Distribution of responses to these two items is visualised in Fig. 2 using mosaic plots.

Fig. 2. Mosaic plots for responses in Portugal and Serbia to the items (a) “Do you find challenging to code algorithms and run programs?”, and (b) “Do you like the 'trial & error' method to develop solutions?”

The main difference in responses to the two items is somewhat greater overall agreement of respondents from Portugal with statements about finding algorithm coding and program running challenging and having a preference for the trial and error method when developing solutions. In the large majority of analysed items (15 out of 17), variation in responses between respondents from Portugal and Serbia was not statistically significant, which further supports the observation that respondents from these two countries are generally similar in terms of their reported entrance knowledge, expectations, and motivation.

5 CONCLUSION

Surveyed students from Portugal and Serbia reported low entrance knowledge in programming, but high expectations regarding their introductory course in programming and high motivation regarding programming in general. There were small differences in overall survey responses between the two countries, in particular

higher entrance knowledge in Serbia and slightly higher mean expectations in Portugal. Responses to individual items were significantly different between the countries only for the motivation-related items about the challenging aspect of programming and the usage of the trial and error method in solution development.

Demand for high-level skills is increasing in the European Union (EU), so EU-level priorities for action include excellence in skills development and support for effective and efficient higher education systems⁵. Solid programming skills are needed today in many professional fields and are commonly taught in engineering education. Nevertheless, the results in the present study suggest that students in both Portugal and Serbia reach higher education with low programming knowledge despite having high motivation, which supports earlier doubts regarding previous education in computing [4]. Improving early education in programming requires vast effort, but there are some corresponding actions at both national and international levels, such as the digital competences initiative *Portugal INCoDe.2030*⁶, introduction of a digital competences framework in Serbia [15], and the *EU Code Week* movement⁷.

As shown in a prior study about introductory programming courses, academic achievement may considerably vary between Portugal and Serbia [4]. It appears that previously observed differences in pass and assessment rates, which are higher in Serbia as opposed to Portugal, cannot be readily explained only by differences in student entrance knowledge, expectations, or motivation, because the surveyed students from Portugal and Serbia were fairly similar in these respects. Students from Serbia reported slightly higher entrance knowledge, but this also might only partially explain considerably higher pass and assessment rates in Serbia.

Further research would be needed to investigate other potential explanations of the achievement discrepancy, e.g., student sociodemographic factors and prospects of starting a career, and differing course content and requirements. Teachers might only have limited options to combat the present achievement trend on their own, such as redesigning the course or applying novel teaching methods and tools. For these reasons, the present study is to be followed by more extensive surveys of students and an investigation into recommendations for programming teachers.

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⁵ EUR-Lex - 52017DC0247, URL: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52017DC0247>

⁶ Portugal INCoDe.2030, URL: <https://www.incode2030.gov.pt>

⁷ Europe Code Week, URL: <https://codeweek.eu>

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